

ROLE OF REHABILITATION IN PANDEMIC CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Despite the tireless research of scientists around the world, we are witnessing the prevalence of coronavirus disease, many questions about the etiology, course, prevention, rehabilitation of the disease remain open. Experiments by health professionals have shown that coronavirus infection was mostly mild to moderate, but severe and lethal cases were observed in about 40 percent of patients. Of course, it was noted that the condition of the patient's immune system, as well as the patient's age, the presence of co-morbidities and harmful habits are of great importance. If a patient with Covid infection is rehabilitated from the first days of his illness and its continuity is established, the rate of not only death but also admission to the intensive care unit of many patients will be sharply reduced [3].

Introduction.

Purpose of the article: To identify, study, analyze the problems encountered in the rehabilitation and continuity of patients with covid-19 infection in pandemic conditions, to improve the work of medical staff, their position in all stages and aspects of rehabilitation and thus ensure effective passage of all stages of rehabilitation. The task is to bring the patient back to pre-pandemic life and prevent complications, fully restore the lost capacity of the organism, in any case to slow down the progression of the disease. To achieve them, a complex of therapeutic and restorative means is used, including exercise, natural factors, various types of massage, exercise in (massage) simulators,

occupational therapy, psychotherapy and those that have the most rehabilitative effect of autotraining. [9]

Research methods: In the process of collecting, processing and analyzing research materials using modern epidemiological, socio-hygienic, mathematical-statistical and evidence-based medical methods to analyze the activities of nurses in the rehabilitation of patients with COVID-19 infection, "Nazarbek Covid 19" center nurses (78) and 134 patients (with their consent) were interviewed. (CQFN - COVID QUESTIONNAIRE FOR NURSES)

Results and analysis. According to the results of the survey: patients were expressed dissatisfaction with the

implementation of rehabilitation measures. When asked if they help the patient with breathing exercises and massages by medical staff, 46% of medical staff said that they do not help due to lack of time, 12% of nurses do not know breathing exercises, 56% of nurses help patients with exercises and regularly perform vibro massage). After the patient

is discharged from the hospital, breathing exercises are very important for at least three months after the illness (especially for those with comorbidities) and are explained by the ward nurse in 48% of cases and by the doctor in 30% of cases, the patient's diet and water balance (50%) by a nurse, (28%) in cases where the doctor is supervising.

(1tab)

The importance and purpose of the treatments and medications taken were also determined when the nurse explained the patient (47%) when asked by the majority of patients (in cases where the patients were medical personnel). Nurses (20%) said that it is important for patients to take the prescribed medication after

leaving the hospital, to do breathing exercises, and that it is important for them to recover. (18%) explained. 48% of patients were satisfied with nursing care, while 52% of patients responded with dissatisfaction.

Agree with the nurse's care

DOES THE NURSE EXPLAIN TOYHE OU IN ADVANCE THE IMPORTANCE AND PURPOSE OF THE PRECEDURES YOU WANT TO PERFORM?

(yes 16/ no 43) (2 tab)

(3tab)

Conclusion

Development of recommendations for improving the rehabilitation process in patients,

- ✓ Involvement of rehabilitation physicians in hospitals (inpatient facilities where patients with COVID-19 infection are treated);
- ✓ Provide rehabilitation programs based on the patient's current condition,
- ✓ Paramedics should be trained to assist the patient in performing

breathing exercises and to use the principles of interviewing in a way that takes into account the patient's mental and emotional state.

Recommend the creation and implementation of an interactive electronic system that connects patients with COVID-19 infection with primary health care facilities and patients in need of rehabilitation, which will allow patients to receive rehabilitation treatments faster and facilitate the work of medical staff.

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